

X-Band Dual-Beam Doppler Radar Observations of the Chesapeake Bay Outflow Plume

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents observations of the Chesapeake Bay outflow plume front made with a new Frequency-Modulated Interrupted Continuous-Wave (FMICW) dual-beam Doppler radar. The radar was deployed aboard the University of Delaware's Cape Henlopen research vessel for participation in the Naval Research Laboratory's (NRL) Chesapeake Bay Outflow Plume Experiments (COPE-I and COPE-II), which took place during September 1996 and May 1997. Relative radar cross-section and surface scatterer velocity vector measurements of the surface manifestation of the plume were made along with sub-surface current measurements made with an acoustic Doppler current profiler. The results show that the surface scatterer velocity obtained with the radar can be very different than that obtained with the current profiler.

INTRODUCTION

Doppler radar measurements can provide useful information about the dynamics of the sea surface [1]-[3]. Generally, such measurements have been made with radar systems employing a single antenna pointed in a fixed azimuth direction. These systems measure the radial component of the sea surface scatterer velocity and, consequently, can only detect if the scatterers are approaching or receding in the line of sight direction. In order to obtain directional information as well as the speed of the sea surface scatterers, we have built a new Frequency Modulated Interrupted Continuous Wave (FMICW) radar

which can make Doppler velocity measurements in two different directions. By combining the velocities from the two look angles, a surface scatterer velocity vector is obtained.

The radar was deployed aboard the R/V Cape Henlopen during the Naval Research Laboratory's (NRL) first and second Chesapeake Bay Outflow Plume Experiments (COPE-I and COPE-II) which took place during September 1996 and May 1997. A towed Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) was also deployed, simultaneously, to provide a comparison of the velocities measured with the two systems. Measurements were made across the surface manifestation of the plume for a number of different environmental conditions. Two cases are presented in this paper. The first example shows results for moderate wind conditions (~3 m/s) and the second shows results for light wind conditions (<0.5 m/s). The vector velocities obtained with the two systems are generally different, especially for the case with the stronger wind conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Fig. 1 shows the dual beam Doppler radar setup. An outrigger which stabilized the ship while underway prevented the fore antenna from being turned any further forward. Therefore, the antennas were placed asymmetrically about the starboard direction as shown. The azimuthal pointing angle of the fore and aft antennas relative to the starboard direction were 1.7 degrees and 31.2 degrees, respectively. Velocity measurements were typically made for

Figure 1. Dual-beam Doppler radar concept.

vertical polarization over a 200 m swath using 4 m resolution to encompass the surface manifestation of the plume, which was typically sampled by sailing parallel to it. As the vessel moved through the water, a patch of the ocean surface was first viewed by the fore antenna and then shortly after viewed by the aft antenna. Velocity measurement from the two directions were then combined to form velocity vectors [4]. A cartesian coordinate system with axes u and v , as shown in Fig. 1, was used for the vector computation. For convenience, since the ship generally sailed parallel to a front, an axis perpendicular to the heading of the ship was used for the u -axis. The v -axis was perpendicular to this axis and pointed in the aft direction as shown.

MODERATE WIND CASE

This first example shows measurements made during COPE-I on 9/25/97 between 1400 and 1700 EDT. For this case, the wind was blowing from the northeast (211 degrees true) at a speed of 2.9 m/s. The front slowly moved offshore during this interval. The approximate positions at three different times are indicated by dotted lines on the chart shown in Fig. 2. The solid line shows the coarse used to sample the plume boundary. Radar measurements were first made between 1400 and 1420 EDT and then between 1600 and 1620 EDT. ADCP measurements were made between 1630 and 1700 EDT. Current velocities obtained with this system for the two different water masses are shown in the lower right corner of Fig. 2. A strong shear along with a weaker convergence occurred across the front.

Vector scatterer velocity measurements are shown for the interval between 1400 and 1420 EDT in Fig. 3. The vectors are shown superimposed on a gray-scale image which represents the u -component of the velocity vector. The vectors are primarily aligned with the v -axis (time axis) on the bay water side of the plume, whereas, they make about a 45 degree angle with it on the ocean water side and,

Figure 2. Coarse used to sample the plume front on 9/25/96 and environmental conditions.

therefore, shows a strong divergence and weak shear across the front. These results are in contrast with the current velocity measurements made with the ADCP device. A similar behavior was observed for the measurements made between 1600 and 1620 EDT. The cause of this discrepancy is currently being investigated but is likely a result of wave-current interaction at the front. The Bragg model is generally used to explain scattering for vertical polarization, even at low grazing angles [5]. Using this model, the scatterer velocity can be shown to be not only a function of the surface currents but of the orbital velocity of the waves as well. Therefore, if the wave-current interaction is strong enough to cause a change in the wave spectral density, it could result in a corresponding change in the scatterer velocity. For the case presented here, waves comparable in length to the radar resolution cell were in fact seen to be

Figure 3. Scatterer velocity vectors superimposed a gray scale image of the u -component for the 9/25/96 case.

moving in opposing directions away from the front which may explain the discrepancy seen between the ADCP and radar derived velocity vectors.

LOW WIND CASE

The measurements for this case were collected during COPE-II on 5/23/97 between 1400 and 1500 EDT. For this case, the wind was very light and blowing towards the northeast (24 degrees true) at a speed of 0.1 m/s. The approximate position of the front and the course used to sample it are shown in Fig. 4. Both radar and ADCP measurements were made simultaneously during this interval. Only relative across (u) and along front (v) ADCP current velocity measurements were available for this case and are indicated at the bottom of the figure. As for the previous case, the ADCP measurements indicate that a strong shear along with a weaker convergence occurred across the front. These changes occurred over a distance of only 4 m.

Vector scatterer velocity measurements are shown in Fig 5. for the interval where the R/V Cape Henlopen crossed the plume front at 1448 EDT. The vectors on the far side of the front (plume water) are turned more in the counter-clockwise direction and are shorter than those on the near side (ocean water), indicating convergence. Even though the radar derived velocity vectors show convergence, in agreement with the ADCP measured currents, they don't show a significant shear. In addition unlike the ADCP measurements, the vectors at the front are turned even further in the counter-clockwise direction and are nearly aligned with the boundary.

Figure 4. Course used to sample the plume front on 5/23/97 and environmental conditions.

Figure 5. Scatterer velocity vectors superimposed upon a gray scale image of the u-component for the 5/23/97 case.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Observations of the surface manifestation of the Chesapeake Bay outflow plume were made using a new dual-beam FMICW radar and ADCP. Two example measurement sets were presented. The first set was made under moderate wind conditions and the second set was made under extremely light wind conditions. The radar derived velocity vectors were seen to be quite different than the ADCP measured current vectors, especially for the stronger wind case. This inconsistency is currently under investigation but is probably caused by modification of wave parameters due to wave-current interaction at the front.

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